

THE JUSTIFICATION OF NEED TO APPLY AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. This article aims to substantiate the integrative approach, which has become necessary for application to all stages of education today, its initial introduction into pedagogy, its importance, and the need for its application to the educational process through theoretical foundations and practical guidelines.

Keywords: integrative approach, educational process, pedagogical systems, main levels of integration, flexible classrooms, online resources.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda ta'limning barcha bosqichlarida qo'llash zaruriyatiga aylangan integrativ yondashuv, uning pedagogika faniga dastlabki kirib kelishi, ahamiyati, ta'lim-tarbiya jarayoniga tatbiq etish zaruriyatini nazariy asoslar va amaliy ko'rsatmalar orqali asoslab berish maqsad qilib qo'yilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: integrativ yondashuv, ta'lim jarayoni, pedagogik tizimlar, integratsiyaning asosiy darajalari, moslashuvchan sinflar, onlayn resurslar.

Аннотация. Данная статья направлена на обоснование интегративного подхода, который стал необходимым для применения на всех этапах образования сегодня, его первоначальное внедрение в педагогику, его важность и необходимость применения к образовательному процессу посредством теоретических основ и практических рекомендаций.

Ключевые слова: интегративный подход, образовательный процесс, педагогические системы, основные уровни интеграции, гибкие классы, онлайн-ресурсы.

Introduction. At every educational level, there is a need to implement an integrative approach to the process that is grounded in contemporary pedagogical ideas. In the first part of the 1980s, the scientific word "integration" was developed in pedagogy and quickly expanded to include social life, economics, politics, information, and other fields. The term "integration" started to be used in education by the 1990s. The new 2022–2026 Uzbekistan Development Strategy lays out education-related tasks. Ideas were specifically shared about strengthening the connection between science and practice in conjunction with esteemed worldwide scientific centers and universities.

Another element of integration is the challenges of maintaining harmony in the curriculum. It generalizes the development of knowledge, concepts, abilities, and competencies in education and parenting and converts them into laws or regulations.

Literature analysis. The analysis of scientific literature shows that the integrative approach has been widely studied in pedagogical theory and practice. The theoretical foundations of integration are based on the constructivist ideas of Lev Vygotsky, who emphasized social interaction and collaborative learning as key factors in cognitive development. Researchers such as R.V.Konchakovsky and L.T.Akhmedova have examined different levels and forms of integration in education, highlighting its systemic

and interdisciplinary nature. Modern studies also focus on the role of innovative technologies and interdisciplinary connections in improving the quality and effectiveness of the educational process.

Research methodology. The research is based on theoretical analysis, comparative study, and generalization of scientific sources related to the integrative approach in education. Methods such as analysis of pedagogical literature, synthesis of theoretical concepts, and systematization were used to justify the necessity of applying an integrative approach in the educational process.

Results and discussion. Integration of the educational process is the unification of the goals and factors of education into a single whole. This involves the organization of systematization of knowledge, incorporating the elements that make up the content of education: knowledge, skills, qualifications, norms, pedagogical systems, the formation of students' skills to understand the mutual integration and comprehensive connection between phenomena, concepts, ideas, theories occurring in technical and technological processes; ensuring that these connections help to deepen scientific and professional knowledge; providing students with the skills to solve creative problems theoretically correctly and practically in an expedient manner, and to correctly formulate the goals, criteria and tasks of technical – economic, social – ecological, organizational – pedagogical systems based on the knowledge and skills acquired in studying various subjects. At each stage, there is a need to introduce an integrative approach to the educational process. In particular, interactive forms of education, technologies – integrative lessons, methods that encourage students to think critically – are rapidly developing in the educational process. Work is underway to organize integrated education, which serves the goal of educating students together by achieving the globalization of education.

The emergence of integrated professions is increasing the role and importance of integrated education in developing the professional competence of future teachers. A number of scientific studies and research are being conducted worldwide to improve the quality and effectiveness of education by integrating teaching and implementing a comprehensive approach. Constructivist theories put forward by L.S.Vygotsky underpin this approach. He argues that students construct their knowledge through interaction with the environment and cooperation with peers [1]. This approach focuses on a more student-centered approach, as opposed to the traditional model. For example, in the case of biology, students are better able to participate in practical experiments and group discussions to learn scientific concepts rather than passively listening to lectures.

According to L.T.Ahmedova, an integrated lesson is a specific and unique form of a lesson that not only combines information from different subjects, but also saves time [2]. The first institution that provided education based on an integrative approach was the California Institute of Integral Studies, founded in 1968 in California, USA. Over the past

decade, Ken Wilber's integrative institute has also emerged in the USA. Education based on integrative education began at the R.Y. Carlos University in Madrid, Spain [3].

Integrated education, first of all, involves bringing together, integrating, and teaching related and compatible subjects in a comprehensive manner. Integrating educational content is of great importance for both the teacher and the learner, and is one of the important factors in improving the quality of education, improving the activity of the learner, activating them, consolidating their knowledge, instilling strong motivation in them, and self-development [4]. The integrative approach is the process of determining a single correct conclusion based on the inextricable connection of the infinitely many small parts that make up the information, their integrity, and unity. This approach is based on the deep content of the didactic system of the knowledge being studied, a systematic approach to knowledge, and teaching students the most appropriate ways to acquire knowledge.

The integrative approach is considered a complex and systematic approach to educational processes, which is useful in introducing systematic analysis research methods and using induction and deduction methods of knowledge. The integrative approach considers education and upbringing as a hierarchical system and guarantees the effectiveness of research conducted on them.

Modern scientific methodological development creates the need for integration of relationships in each discipline. At the same time, along with the processes of differentiation in the disciplines, the need for synthesis and integration of scientific information has also increased. The integration process requires a new look at the science of biology, creating the need to search for new paradigms. As a result of the integration processes that have taken place in geography itself, integrative directions that connect natural and socio-economic geography (reclamation biology, recreational biology, biology of nature use, etc.) have emerged [6]. R.V. Konchakovsky divides integration into following four main levels [4]:

Figure 1. Four main levels of integration

In his opinion, *systemic integration* is based on the union of two disciplines and leads to the emergence of a new science in a new scientific process. *Model integration* is based on the union of functional and structural models with other disciplines. *Complex integration* is characterized by a simultaneous complex description of various social sciences and the interrelationship between different levels of their teaching. *Analytical integration* is based on the analysis of achievements in relevant fields based on scientific data, the study of their impact on social life and their practical use. L.P. Elinkon also emphasizes the importance of integrating school education, considering “integration as a means of effectively organizing lessons, a form of raising the connections between subjects to new levels” [5]. Modern pedagogical approaches use technology to enhance the learning experience.

The introduction of an integrative approach to the educational process ensures systematic, effective and practical acquisition of knowledge. This serves to develop not only knowledge for students, but also creativity, critical thinking and the ability to adapt to different fields.

Blended learning, flexible classrooms, and online resources provide students with flexibility in their learning content. Educational technology allows for the creation of personalized learning experiences tailored to individual needs and preferences [6]. An integrative approach involves taking into account and relying on knowledge, skills, competencies, and experience from different disciplines, that is, integrating and developing communicative, professional, and social competence in a foreign language. This approach involves the use of new innovative technologies aimed at developing students' free communication skills, and developing students' skills to work independently and in teams.

Conclusion. This approach has led to a significant positive change in the quality of education and increased students' motivation to learn the language. The integrative approach is one of the principles of modern and effective education, which forms a multifaceted image and worldview in learners, encourages them to think and reason in new ways, allows them to easily and quickly master knowledge and arouses motivation, creates the opportunity to freely apply the knowledge gained from the disciplines in practice, and also helps to understand the world as a whole and form the idea that systems are interconnected.

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